

GAMA RADIATION EFFECT ON THERMOGRAVIMETRIC PROPERTIES AND INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY OF SISAL FIBERS / POLYURETHANE DERIVED FROM CASTOR OIL COMPOSITES WITHOUT COUPLING AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

An alternative to materials used in radiotherapy and radiology rooms can be composites based on natural fibers and polyurethane derived from castor oil, which may present chemical bonding between the components of the polymer and the lignin of the fiber. The incidence of radiation can lead to degradation of polymeric material and change its mechanical properties. The objective of this study was to verify the possibility of chemical affinity between polyurethane derived from castor oil and sisal fibers, without use of coupling agents, through thermogravimetric analysis and infrared spectroscopy, before and after the incidence of gamma irradiation, dose of 25 kGy. The composites were obtained by manual mixture of fibers and matrix with 1,0:1,0 mass proportion of the components, cold pressed with average pressure of 1.8 kPa for 24 hours until complete cure of the polymer. It was observed through thermogravimetric analysis that both dispersed fibers and woven composites present thermal stability until 200°C without gamma irradiation, meaning that the materials are solvent-free. The incidence of gamma radiation increases the degradation temperature, indicating that radiation main effect on these materials is not degradation, but the crosslinking of polymeric chains. Also through this analysis was determined that the materials present mass proportion of 80% fibers to 20% polymer. Infrared spectroscopy indicated evidences of chemical bonding between polyurethane, which present isocyanate (NCO radicals), and sisal fibers, which present lignine (OH radicals). That can increase the load transfer between matrix and fibers, increasing mechanical properties of the composites. The incidence of gamma radiation has shown alterations on the infrared spectrum, indicating that radiation can increase bonding between polyurethane and sisal fibers. There were also indications of degradation of the fibers after gamma irradiation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesives encountered in furniture and accessories for radiotherapy and radio diagnostics are commonly produced from non-renewable sources using large amounts of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) [1-3], substances which damage to human health vary from respiratory tract and skin irritation, headaches, tiredness and loss of focus [4] until hearing loss [5] and possible appearance of several types of cancer [6-8]. A way to substitute materials that use VOCs aiming eco-friendliness and

the diminishing of damage to both patients and workers may be the use of green composites. These composites combine natural fibers with polymeric matrixes of renewable or recycled sources.

One of the most versatile types of polymers is the polyurethanes, materials which are produced through the chemical reaction between hydroxyl compounds and isocyanates [9]. These polymers may be obtained by the pre-polymer system, utilizing polyols (compounds that present hydroxyls) and pre-polymers (compounds that present isocyanates) in order to produce a higher molecular mass compound before performing the reaction of the final product [1]. The polyol utilized in polyurethane resins can be derived of petrol or of other sources, including natural oils like soy, canola, corn, palm and castor [10]. Polyurethane derived from castor oil presents several advantages when compared to other types of polymers. Regarding synthetic polymers its differential is not to exhale VOCs [11] and regarding other vegetable-based polymers, the fact that its raw material is not utilized as food.

When it comes to natural raw materials with potential use in engineering, natural fibers show some advantages when compared to synthetic ones. Natural fibers have lower density, satisfying specific elastic modulus, high processing flexibility and high specific stiffness besides being more economically attractive when compared to synthetic ones, which make it an interesting and ecologically friendly alternative [12-15]. Several different researches [16-27] were performed aiming to investigate the behavior of composites that have as components natural fibers when submitted to different loading and aiming utilization in diverse industry fields. These composites showed to have good mechanical properties and possibility of substituting parts made of synthetic materials in the suggested applications. Sisal fibers were studied combined with polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate, epoxy and other types of matrixes, proving to be rather promising as engineering materials, but still presenting matrix-fiber interface problems.

Generally, hydrophilic natural fibers employed as composite reinforcements don't present good adhesion with polymers, essentially hydrophobic, employed as composite matrixes. That leads to the necessity of using coupling agents as a way to improve load transfer between matrix and reinforcement. Several methods can be applied [28], one of them being the removal of lignin from the fibers. The problem with these processes lay in the generation of toxic residuals and in the necessity of one extra step in the composite production. To possibly avoid these issues the combination between polyurethane derived from castor oil and sisal fibers was purposed, since the molecular structure of lignin shows radicals that may chemically interact with the free isocyanate of the polyurethane. This can enhance the bond in the interface matrix-fiber, increasing load transfer and improving mechanical properties without employing coupling agents.

Polymers subjected to high energy radiation, as the materials utilized in furniture of radiotherapy and radio diagnosis rooms, have its mechanical properties altered considerably [29]. Among the many types of radiation employed as treatment and examination we can cite gamma radiation, a high-frequency electromagnetic type produced by disintegrating radioactive elements [30]. The interactions between radiation and polymers may be of several kinds, covering from no deviation of path to degradation of the polymeric chain, being even possible the occurrence of mechanical properties increase. These processes occur simultaneously with predominance of one of them, depending on the chemical structure of the material and radiation dose [31].

Azevedo [32, 33] have studied the effect of gamma radiation over polyurethane derived from castor oil specimens, both of adhesives and foam, trough mechanic and surface testing, concluding that this type of radiation has as consequence the enhancement of chain crosslinking. According to Varghese [29] sisal fibers have good resistance to ageing. The combination of these two materials may lead to a composite with very good behavior regarding radiation resistance and naturally enhanced interaction between fiber and matrix. The objective of this study was to verify the possibility of chemical affinity between polyurethane derived from castor oil and sisal fibers, without use of coupling agents, trough thermogravimetric analysis and infrared spectroscopy, before and after the incidence of gamma irradiation, dose of 25 kGy, usually applied as sterilizing dose in medical materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Raw Materials

Polyurethane derived from castor oil was donated by the company Cequil, from Araraquara – SP, BR. It's presented as a bi-component, a polyol and a pre-polymer. The preparation was realized according to provider's specifications, keeping 1,0:1,0 mass proportion of pre-polymer and polyol. Sisal fibers were acquired in the local commerce of the city of Curitiba – PR, BR. There was no concern regarding the precedence of the fibers, since this monitoring would lead to an increase of project costs. Two geometries were utilized: (1) dispersed fibers of 5mm length and (2) bidirectional sisal woven of 2mm thickness. The only previous processing of the fibers was drying in stove at 70°C for 6h.

2.2 Composites

The specimens were moulded by pressure, formed by rectangular plaques of 3 to 4 mm thickness. Matrix and fibres were manually mixed with mass proportion of 80% fibres to 20% resin, leaked into Teflon plates and pressed utilizing 6 ton. Load, equivalent to 266,6 N/m² pressure. The processes were performed at room temperature without employment of vacuum and the resin was left to cure for 24h before mold release.

Gamma radiation, dose of 25 kGy, was applied by the company Embrarad of Cotia – SP, BR, utilizing industrial Cobalt 60 source MDS Nordion's JS-9600.

2.3 Analysis

To Thermogravimetric Analysis, TGA, was used a thermoscale Perkin Elmer, model STA 6000 in the following conditions: Sample mass: 4,0 to 5,0 mg; Temperature scale: 50 °C to 800 °C; Heating rate: 10 °C/min; N₂ atmosphere: 20 ml/min.

Infrared spectroscopy analysis was performed through attenuated total reflectance method, ATR, using a Perkin Elmer equipment model FT-IR Spectrometer Frontier.

Both tests were performed at Thermal and Spectroscopy Analysis of Fuels and Materials of UTFPR campus Medianeira.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermogravimetric Analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis was made with the objective of studying the thermal stability of sisal fibers, polyurethane derived from castor oil and the resultant composites before and after exposure to a 25kGy dose of gamma radiation. Figure 1 shows the comparison of obtained curves for the composite of dispersed fibers, polyurethane and dispersed fibers before and after irradiation.

Figure 1 – Comparison of TGA curves for composites and compounds (a) before and (b) after irradiation.

When analyzing Figure 1 it's possible to notice that the dispersed fibers curves in both cases present start of thermal events happens at 50 °C, continuing until 250 °C, due to the presence of water [34]. After that there is another thermal event from 250 °C until 370 °C assigned to degradation of cellulose and hemicellulose [35]. From 370 °C to 420 °C lignin degrades [36], with quasi-stabilization of mass loss after 420 °C, being considered as final temperature of degradation.

Considering the test curves of polyurethane, there can be noticed differences between non-irradiated and irradiated materials. In the case of non-irradiated polymer thermal events are observed in two different stages, the first starting at 250 °C and finishing at 350 °C related to the degradation of pre-polymer [32], and the second starting at 350 °C and finishing at 520 °C related to degradation of polyol [32]. The absence of thermal events before 200 °C indicates that the material doesn't present solvents in its composition. After the incidence of gamma radiation this polymer has its thermal events dislocated to higher temperatures, what can be justified by the enhancement of chain crosslinking. Pre-polymer degradation starts at 260 °C going to 350 °C, while polyol degradation happens from 350 °C to 550 °C [32].

Composites behavior can be described as a balance between the behaviors of its components, related to the volumetric rate of each. It is then expected that in this case the demeanor of the composite is more approximate to the one presented by sisal fibers. When comparing before and after irradiation curves, it can be seen that the temperatures of start of degradation remain the same in both cases (60 °C) but after gamma radiation incidence the finishing temperature present a drop on its value (from 150 °C to 100 °C), probably due to fiber degradation.

Figure 2 shows the comparison of obtained curves for the composite of woven fibers, polyurethane and woven fibers before and after irradiation.

Figure 2 – Comparison of TGA curves for composites and compounds (a) before and (b) after irradiation.

The behavior presented on the curves of Figure 2 is very similar to the one observed on the other composite. The slight differences may be attributed to previous treatments realized on the woven fibers before commercialization.

3.2 Infrared Spectroscopy Analysis

Figure 3 shows the spectrum obtained through FT-IR ATR of the specimens of dispersed fibers composite, polyurethane and dispersed fibers before gamma radiation exposure.

Figure 3 – FT-IR ATR spectrum of dispersed fibers, polyurethane and resultant composite before gamma irradiation.

Figure 4 shows the spectrum obtained through FT-IR ATR of the specimens of dispersed fibers composite, polyurethane and dispersed fibers after gamma radiation exposure.

Figure 4 – FT-IR ATR spectrum of dispersed fibers, polyurethane and resultant composite after gamma irradiation.

Figure 3 shows that the composite curve presents reduction of intensity in the isocyanate peak (NCO) at 2230 cm^{-1} and hydroxyl peak (OH) at 3370 cm^{-1} when compared to the curves of the isolated materials, indicating that there might be chemical affinity between the isocyanate and hydroxyl groups of the composite components.

When comparing with Figure 4 the effect of gamma radiation incidence can be observed. The fibers present increase of intensity in the peaks of C-H bonding of the fibers aromatic rings, regions of 2900 – 3000 cm^{-1} . The polyurethane after irradiation present accentuated diminishing of NCO peak intensity when compared to the non-irradiated material. That indicates crosslinking enhancement due to radiation, also observed by [32]. Regarding the composite, the isocyanate peak at 2230 cm^{-1} has kept its intensity when compared to the one of the polyurethane submitted to gamma radiation, but urethane and amides peaks had its intensities increased.

Figure 5 shows the spectrum obtained through FT-IR ATR of the specimens of woven fibers composite, polyurethane and woven fibers before gamma radiation exposure.

Figure 5 – FT-IR ATR spectrum of woven fibers, polyurethane and resultant composite before gamma irradiation.

Figure 6 shows the spectrum obtained through FT-IR ATR of the specimens of woven fibers composite, polyurethane and woven fibers after gamma radiation exposure.

Figure 6 – FT-IR ATR spectrum of woven fibers, polyurethane and resultant composite after gamma irradiation.

Figure 5 shows that the composite curve presents reduction of intensity in the isocyanate peak (NCO) at 2230 cm^{-1} and hydroxyl peak (OH) at 3370 cm^{-1} when compared to the curves of the isolated materials, indicating that there might be chemical affinity between the isocyanate and hydroxyl groups of the composite components. It can also be noticed that this reduction is not as intense as presented by the dispersed fibers composite, what can be a result both of less chemical affinity due to previous chemical treatments and to less available wetting area of the woven material.

When comparing with Figure 6 the effect of gamma radiation incidence can be observed. The fibers present increase of intensity in the peaks of C-H bonding of the fibers aromatic rings, regions of $2900 - 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Regarding the composite, the isocyanate peak at 2230 cm^{-1} has kept its intensity when compared to the one of the polyurethane submitted to gamma radiation, but urethane and amides peaks had its intensities increased.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Through thermogravimetric analysis it is possible to conclude that the composites present thermal stability until $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ even after gamma radiation incidence and that solvents are not employed in its composition. The thermal behavior of the composites is approximated to the one shown by the fibers due to its bigger volumetric fraction in the material.

Infrared spectroscopy has indicated the possibility of chemical interaction between NCO radicals of the polyurethane derived from castor oil with the OH radicals of the fibers, what increases interaction on the fiber/matrix interface. Also, evidences of degradation of the fibers after the incidence of 25 kGy dose of gamma radiation were noticed.

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